

**Perceived Impact of the Contributory Health Insurance Scheme among Enrolled Staff of
Local Government Councils in Kano State, Nigeria**

BY

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Abstract

This study assessed the employees' perceived satisfaction with the State Health Insurance Scheme in Nigeria, using Kano State Contributory Health Insurance Scheme. The objectives of the study are to assess the employees' perception on the quality of the healthcare delivery under the health insurance scheme and examine the effect of healthcare quality on patients' satisfaction in the health facilities under the health insurance scheme in Kano State. The study employed a survey research methodology. The population for the study was a total number of 892 employees who were identified through multistage cluster sampling. Sample of 269 subjects for the study was drawn using the krejcie and Morgan's table for determining sample size. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire entitled the Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire III (PSQ3). The reliability of the questionnaire was at 0.72 level of coefficient using Crombach Alpha. The data was analysed using Stata 14 software through quantile regression. Findings of the study revealed that the employees' perception on the quality of the healthcare delivery and the effect of healthcare quality on patients' satisfaction are increasing in the health facilities under the health insurance scheme in Kano State. The study recommended that there is the need for Kano State government to invest more on mobilisation and education to create awareness among enrolees to actively participate in the scheme, and the State government should provide adequate manpower development programmes which will serve a dual purpose of promoting skill acquisition and at the same time foster good healthcare seeking behaviour in addition to awareness creation among employees.

Keywords: Impact, Contributory, Health, Insurance

Introduction

Health insurance schemes are expected to provide adequate, efficient, improved and qualitative

healthcare services that meet patients' satisfaction. This has resulted in Health insurance schemes embarking on intensive research projects and surveys to find out ways of satisfying patients healthcare needs. Thus, Medical care organizations may undertake consumer satisfaction research to ascertain patients' needs and to also improve on the healthcare quality of the health organizations (Lin and Kelly, 1995; Gill and White, 2009). Healthcare quality from the patients' point of view has only been researched in recent times and only few measuring instruments have been explicitly developed for measuring healthcare quality from patient's perspective. Patients are the pivot whose opinion provides critical lessons into the quality of healthcare systems, which might lead to customer satisfaction and long-term profitable relationship. LaVela and Gallan (2014) confirms that patients' satisfaction may lead to positive outcome such as loyalty for healthcare organizations.

The categorical importance of service quality in business and marketing literature cannot be over emphasized. Basically quality of service donates the ability of service providers to satisfy the needs and wants of their consumers. The most frequently used theoretical model for measuring the satisfaction of consumer service quality (SERVQUAL) model developed is by Parassuraman Berry, and Zeithaml, (1991). Although, there is no universal definition of service quality but many see it as a dual function of individual perspective and the context used. According to Mosadeghrad, (2014) Quality is 'value'; 'excellence'; 'conformance to specifications'; 'conformance to requirements'; 'fitness for use'; 'meeting and/or exceeding customers' expectations', and 'consistently delighting the customer by providing products and services according to the latest functional specifications which meet and exceed the customer's explicit and implicit needs and satisfy producer/provider''.

With regards to aspect magnitude or dimension of service quality Ibrahim and Ssendiwala,

(2014) highlighted the empirical propositions of Parasuraman, et al, (1985) who proposed ten dimensions of service quality and later revised them to five. Subsequently, Grönroos, (1988) proposed a similar model; Parasuraman et al, (1985) argued that these dimensions characterised what “consumers use in forming expectations about and perceptions of services”.

Reliability is the most important dimension of the service quality attributes to the customer. Reliability has been defined as the ability of the service provider to deliver services as promised or as patients hope for. In other words, service providers should comply with their communication claims about their services and the kind of services the facility communicates it performs. Ibrahim and Ssendiwala (2014) pointed the most important aspect of quality of service according to customers being the ability of the service provider to deliver on their promises consistently. Responsiveness as key quality refers to the readiness of service providers to help customers and to offer quick service. Customers assessed a service provider’s responsiveness by measuring the time it takes the service providers to respond to serve their service needs, that is requests, questions, complaints, and problems. In this case, for patients, responsiveness means the care and attention given by healthcare givers during hospital visits by patients.

Assurance as the third dimension is donated to mean the knowledge of employees, courtesy, and the ability of the firm to inspire trust and customer confidence. This dimension is of particular relevance to service firms engaged in high levels of credence qualities, such as health insurance schemes. The assurance dimension is very important due to the perceived risk experienced by consumers and the need to give assurance to consumers of quality service delivery (Ibrahim and Ssendiwala, 2014). Since it is very difficult for patients to evaluate and or

assessed the outcome of the service prior to seeking it, healthcare workers need to give assurance on the delivery of qualitative healthcare to reduce any perceived risk or doubt patients might have.

Empathy as the fourth dimension is introduced to denote the caring and personalized attention given to customers. Ibrahim and Ssendiwala, (2014) emphasized that customers assessed the service firm's empathy by the nature of individualised service they receive. Customers wish to receive personalised services and the service provider recognises and addresses individual needs. In dealing with medical care delivery, care givers must display empathy to patients by being friendly, polite and showing extra care as it aids in quick recovery of patients.

The fifth and the last dimension of service quality concerns the 'Tangibility' that is the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials of the service firms. Since it is difficult for customers (patients) to assessed the level of service they would receive at a particular health facility, healthcare facilities need to be of quality standard in terms of appearance of the building, equipment, healthcare staff, and communication materials like folders and prescription forms. Patients thus, would evaluate the overall healthcare quality by looking at these five quality dimensions during their service meetings. Healthcare facilities and workers must therefore keep in mind the significance of these dimensions of service quality when dealing with patients at all times to guarantee a positive overall evaluation of their services.

However, with regards to patient's expectations, Olson and Dover, (1979) pointed to the beliefs about a product or service that customers seek to receive from their service firms. When patients/customers are not in the know to any information about the service providers, prior expectation of service does not come to play. In reality, however, patients/customers are privy to

vast amount of information about the service provider that influences their service expectations. According to Zeithaml, Berry and Parasuraman, (1993) the sources of information might come from different sources including the firm itself word of mouth expert opinion publicity communication from the company as well as prior exposure to competitive services.

Service Quality in Healthcare

According to WHO (2006), quality has some key dimensions these dimensions require that health care be “Efficient, Accessible, Acceptable/patient- centered Equitable and Safe According to Drain (2001) medical care organizations are expected to improve on their service quality delivery in tandem to consumer needs. Healthcare services unlike manufactured goods are difficult to evaluate due to its intangible nature. Service characteristics such as “intangibility heterogeneity and simultaneity make it difficult to define and measure healthcare quality” (Ofili 2014). Physical or tangible goods on the other hand due to their tangibility nature are easily accessed and evaluated before or after consumption. Assessment of healthcare quality is therefore only possible during the interactions in the service process.

According to Mosadeghrad (2014), healthcare services vary from service providers, patients and even locations and time of service delivery. This is due to the “heterogeneity” in services which makes it difficult to provide similar services from different professionals that is physicians, nurses, pharmacists. Assessment of quality therefore becomes difficulty in such a situation as services are not standardized. Healthcare services are performed the same time as its being consumed and this makes it impossible to inventor services for later consumption. This makes it also difficult to control quality as patients or customers are not able to assess service until after consumption. Therefore, this makes healthcare quality a hard task to achieve and measure

(Mosadeghrad, 2014).

Czepiel, (1990) stated that service quality consists of two dimensions. These are technical (output quality) and functional (process quality). These dimensions were evaluated according to “attitudes and behaviour appearance and personality service mindedness accessibility and approachability of customer contact personnel” (Jafarpour, 2006). Furthermore, Czepiel, (1990) cited three dimensions of the service encounter; customer perceptions, provider characteristics and production realities. They argued that these dimensions cover central aspect of service delivery and each of these factors contributes the same way in attaining satisfaction (Jafarpour, 2006). Patient satisfaction has been a widely studied subject in healthcare literature. Patient’s satisfaction with healthcare delivery is very important for medical providers, patients and other third party stakeholders in the healthcare sector. The healthcare industry is one of the most patronised sectors and one that has the most direct contacts between providers and receivers of the service. Contemporarily, various empirical studies revealed that lot of people troop to healthcare facilities in search of remedies or solutions to their health problems. Therefore, assessing patients’ satisfaction can bring new changes in approach or modification in healthcare delivery to ensure service excellence.

Statement of the Problem

Projections from the 2006 census reveals that States in Nigeria range in population from about 12-13 million, with Kano State being the most populous among the 36 States of the federation, and has the largest number of public service employees in the country. This demographic feature presents the state with a large pool of working population without health insurance. In essence, lack of Access to affordable healthcare continues to be a challenge for most of the state residents due to high levels of poverty (especially in the rural areas) and significant reliance on out of

pocket payments. It is on this premise that Kano State comes up with its insurance scheme in 2016 to ensure that every resident has access to good healthcare service, protect families from the financial hardship of huge medical bills and to ensure equitable distribution of health care cost among depreciate income groups. According to its management, the state health insurance/contributory scheme had commence operation for almost 6 years, and had become successful with over 370,000 enrollees accessing healthcare. The scheme is presently operating in 245 health facilities, comprising 134 primary healthcare facilities, 37 secondary healthcare facilities and 74 private healthcare facilities across the state. It is in line with this that this study attempts to measure employees' perception about the quality of service delivery of Kano State contributory health insurance scheme.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the perceptions f employees on the quality of service delivery by the Kano State contributory health insurance scheme. Other objectives of the study are:

1. To assess the employees' perception on the quality of the healthcare delivery under the health insurance scheme in Kano State, and
2. Examine the effect of healthcare quality on patients' satisfaction in the health facilities under the health insurance scheme in Kano State.

Study Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested during this study:

H1 there is no significant relationship between healthcare quality and employees' satisfaction

H2 there is no significant influence between healthcare quality and employees' expectation of services

H3 there is no significant influence between employees' expectation of services and employees' satisfaction

Methodology

This study employs a survey research methodology using the quantitative techniques for data collection and data analysis. The population for the study involves the entire employees of the 44 local government councils in Kano State who are engaged as the participants that pay for monthly contributory health insurance scheme. According to the data obtained from the administrators of the scheme a total number of eight hundred and ninety two (892) employees were identified through multistage cluster sampling. Sample for the study was drawn using the krejcie and Morgan's table for determining sample size from a given population. According to the table a population of 892 has selected a sample of 269 subjects. However, to improve precision and avoid sampling error 270 subjects was used as sample. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire entitled the Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire III (PSQ3) developed by Ware, Snyder and Wright (1976) and the SERVQUAL model developed by Parassuraman, et al, (1998). The PSQIII is a patient satisfaction questionnaire items which contains 50 items. In essence the study adopted the modified version of the PSQ3 which contains 18 items measuring seven main items, "General satisfaction technical quality, interpersonal manner, communication, financial aspects, time spent with doctor and accessibility and convenience" (Ware, Snyder, and Wright, 1976). The reliability of the questionnaire was at 0.72 level of coefficient using Crombach Alpha. A multistage cluster sampling procedure was

employed in the selection of respondents from the three senatorial zones, while 3 local government councils were selected from each senatorial zone. In each selected local government council, a department was randomly selected and from the departments a section was selected, and from each section respondents were selected randomly, and the sample size of 270 respondents were used. Data was however, collected through elect and decide to use quantile regression as it's expected to yield the desired outcome. The data analysis in this study was through quantile regression that constitutes a feasible approach for the modeling of such data since it lacks any distributional assumptions. It is obvious that through this method there are two underlying populations which explain that particular distribution of the data: individuals who are willing to provide a negative evaluation to one or more items proposed in the questionnaire and those who will always provide a completely positive evaluation irrespective of the item. However, after carrying out the administration of the instrument for data collection in this study, only 237 questionnaires were successfully returned. Therefore the analysis of data in this study was based on the retrieved questionnaires.

Interpretation

Table 1, summary statistics of socioeconomic and demographic variables of the respondents

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
stf	237	3	1.310895	1	5

che2	237	.6328502	.4831964	0	1
hsq	237	2.352657	1.155939	1	5
expect	237	2.642512	1.249361	1	5
edu	231	3.313433	.7323037	1	5

cgp	196	.4591837	.4996074	0	1
hia	234	.8235294	.3821579	0	1
fs	232	6.133663	3.907762	1	14
mexp	198	6540.404	8701.968	2500	7500
hise	207	.7101449	.4547948	0	1
age2	237	4.009662	1.980464	1	7

Table 1 above presents the socioeconomic, demographic satisfaction and health related variables of the respondents, this includes age, family size, level of education, medical expenditure per month, health insurance awareness, level of satisfaction, health insurance enrollment, healthcare quality, and expectation about healthcare services. With regards to the age of the respondents about 27% are between the ages of 18 to 30years, 18% are between the ages of 30 to 40years, 33% are between the ages of 41 to 50years, while the rest of 32% are between 51 to 60years of age. Educational level of the respondents reveals that 2% represents primary school holders, 18% are secondary school leavers, with 50% representing ND and NCE, While HND/ BSC represents 29% and only 2% possessed postgraduate qualifications. Responses regarding the rating of quality of healthcare delivery about 50% of the report range between excellences to good quality, 18% reported poor, while about 31% reported dissatisfaction with a very poor comment. Responses the about other principal variables of the model such as Expectation and satisfaction level are on the averages, and that there is strong relationship among them as indicated in table 2 below.

Table 2. correlate stf hsq expect
hise
(obs=207)

	stf	hsq	expec	hise
stf	1.0000			
hsq	0.5865	1.0000		
expec	0.0000	0.6919	1.0000	
hise	-0.5896	-0.0447	-0.0636	1.0000

Marginal effect after quartile regression of healthcare satisfaction model.

VARIABLES	DY/DX	SES..ERR	P - VALUE
AGE	<u>-0.347</u>	<u>0.07114</u>	<u>0.163</u>
FS	<u>0.1908</u>	<u>0.0371</u>	<u>0.004</u>
EDU	<u>0.352</u>	<u>0.18725</u>	<u>0.077</u>
EPEC	<u>0.1166</u>	<u>0.11528</u>	<u>0.004</u>
CHE2*	<u>-0.086</u>	<u>0.2976</u>	<u>0.663</u>
CGP*	<u>-0.097</u>	<u>0.2897</u>	<u>0.011</u>
HSQ	<u>0.088743</u>	<u>0.12538</u>	<u>0.008</u>
HIA*	<u>-0.172</u>	<u>0.3837</u>	<u>0.007</u>
HISE*	<u>-0.102</u>	<u>0.3144</u>	<u>0.067</u>

Dy/dx
marginal
effect
*significance
@ 10% ** @ 5%
*** @ 1%

Table 3, above present the result of marginal effect after quantile regression for the perceived healthcare satisfaction model, empirical findings from the model suggest that educational level

of the respondents is an important predictor of perceived satisfaction with health insurance scheme, that any increase in additional educational level completed satisfaction about service .quality will increase by 35%, this is in lined with our a priori expectation that those who are educated are more enlighten about the quality of healthcare services delivered. The variable Consultation of General Practitioner CGP is introduced to proxy the presence of serious illness it is statistically significant at 10% that any increase in consultant visit will decrease the perceived satisfaction with 9.7%. CHE2 donate catastrophic health expenditure incurred by the patient in the last six month, findings suggest that any catastrophic out of pocket expenditure incurred will lead to decrease in satisfaction about the service delivery quality by 8.6%. HISE stands for health insurance enrollment status, a priori we expect enrollment to foster satisfaction but, the reality is 6 years after commencement about 30% of the employees are yet to be enrolled, findings with regard to this predict HISE as a reducing function of satisfaction with about 10%. HSQ stands for healthcare service quality, finding with regard to it suggest that any additional increase in quality of healthcare delivery will lead to 8.8% increase in satisfaction with health insurance scheme performance., however the empirical suggestion from other variables like family size, expectation, and age of the respondents demonstrate a mixed result as they violet our models a priori expectation..

With regards to research hypothesis, both H1, and H3 can inferred from the quantile regression model that both quality of healthcare delivery and expectation are increasing function of employees' satisfaction with health insurance scheme with magnitude of 11.6% and 8.8 % respectively.

Findings

From the preceding data analysis the following findings are deduced:

1. The employees' perception on the quality of the healthcare delivery under the health insurance scheme is increasing in Kano State.
2. The effect of healthcare quality on patients' satisfaction in the health facilities under the health insurance scheme is increasing in Kano State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study which revealed that the employees' perception on the quality of the healthcare delivery under the health insurance scheme is increasing in Kano State, hence, using quantile regression, which is rated best among other competing models like linear regression, binary logit, and two-part model. The overall significance of the model is satisfactory that is the covariates are jointly statistically significant. The explanatory power of educational level of the respondents is highly recognized that with increase in educational level completed satisfaction with the healthcare services increases by 35%. This finding is in line with that of Ofili (2014) that level of education is an increasing function of individuals' perceived service quality of health insurance scheme. Also among variables of interest Consultation of General Practitioner CGP is introduced to proxy the presence of serious illness it is statistically significant at 10% that any increase in consultant visit will decrease the perceived satisfaction with 9.7%. CHE2 donate catastrophic health expenditure incurred by the patient in the last six month, findings suggest that any catastrophic out of pocket expenditure incurred will lead to decrease in satisfaction about the service delivery quality by 8.6%. HISE stands for health insurance enrollment status, a priori we expect enrollment to foster satisfaction but, the reality is 6 years after commencement about 30% of the employees are yet to be enrolled, findings with regard to this predict HISE as a reducing function of satisfaction

with about 10%. HSQ stands for healthcare service quality, finding with regard to it suggest that any additional increase in quality of healthcare delivery will lead to 8.8% increase in satisfaction with health insurance scheme performance., however the empirical suggestion from other variables like family size, expectation, and age of the respondents demonstrate a mixed result as they violet our models a priori expectation. This study findings relates to the findings of Mosadeghrad, (2014); Ibrahim and Ssendiwala, (2014), and (Jafarpour, 2006).

Regarding the second finding of this study which revealed that the effect of healthcare quality on patients' satisfaction in the health facilities under the health insurance scheme is increasing in Kano State, both H1, and H3 can inferred from the quantile regression model that both quality of healthcare delivery and expectation are increasing function of employees' satisfaction with health insurance scheme with magnitude of 11.6% and 8.8 % respectively. This finding is similar with the findings reported in the studies conducted by LaVela and Gallan, (2014); Mosadeghrad, (2014), and Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, (1985).

Conclusion

As this study investigated the employees' perceived satisfaction about healthcare services delivered by Kano State contributory health insurance scheme using quantile regression. The overall significance of the model is satisfactory that is the covariates are jointly statistically significant. The explanatory power of educational level of the respondents is highly recognised that with increase in educational level completed satisfaction with the healthcare services increases. However, enrollment status of the respondents has become an increasing function of perceived satisfaction with health insurance scheme. This study furthermore justified the importance of education in healthcare demand. Quality of healthcare delivery can be manipulated and influence by government policy through adequate budgetary provisions for

the health insurance scheme, in essence this appropriation can also be used to anticipate the incidence of catastrophic health expenditure by the employees which will in turn lead to more expectation and desired satisfaction with health insurance scheme.

Recommendations

In line with the objectives of this study the following recommendations are provided:

1. There is the need for Kano State government to invest more on mobilisation and education to create awareness among enrollees to actively participate in the scheme.
2. The State government should provide adequate manpower development programmes which will serve a dual purpose of promoting skill acquisition and at the same time foster good healthcare seeking behaviour in addition to awareness creation among employees.

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